

Suicidal ideation in the perinatal period: Characteristics, risk and protective factors in Spanish women with postpartum depression

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ABSTRACT

Background: Despite its serious consequences, there is still a limited body of literature on suicidal ideation during the perinatal period, particularly among women with postpartum depression.

Aim: The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of suicidal ideation in women with postpartum depression, to identify associated risk and protective factors, and to explore moderating variables in the relationship between suicidal ideation and postpartum depression.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted with 91 Spanish postpartum women, recruited via social media and midwives. All participants scored ≥ 11 on the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) and had given birth within the past year. Suicidal ideation was assessed using item 10 of the EPDS.

Findings: 27.5 % of women with postpartum depression reported suicidal ideation. Number of children, postpartum depression and bonding difficulties with the baby were identified as explanatory factors for suicidal ideation. Furthermore, lack of emotional support from family, economic difficulties, anxiety symptoms during pregnancy and baby's irritable temperament were found to moderate the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation.

Conclusion: These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of perinatal suicidal ideation and suggest potential screening and intervention strategies aimed at preventing its onset. Identifying both risk and protective factors is crucial for midwives and mental health professionals to support maternal well-being and prevent adverse psychological outcomes.

Introduction

The puerperal period is defined as spanning from birth to 12 months postpartum, during which numerous physiological, psychological, and social changes occur (Jones & Smith, 2009; Rodríguez-Muñoz et al., 2023). These changes increase the risk of developing mental health disorders in mothers (Bright et al., 2022; Rodríguez-Muñoz et al., 2023). Common symptoms include intense sadness, loss of enjoyment, low energy or motivation, excessive worry, impaired concentration, and feelings of guilt or hopelessness (WHO, 2022). Depression and anxiety are the most prominent disorders (California Task Force on the Status of Maternal Mental Health Care, 2017), affecting 10-20 % of women during this period (Dowse et al., 2020).

These problems affect not only the mother's health but also the child and the surrounding environment (Bright et al., 2022; WHO, 2022). Specifically, maternal mental health problems have been associated

with difficulties in bonding and in establishing a secure attachment with the infant. Children of affected mothers are more likely to show emotional regulation difficulties, behavioral and learning problems, and poorer cognitive development (California Task Force on the Status of Maternal Mental Health Care, 2019). These effects appear to stem from mothers' difficulties in perceiving and adequately responding to their infants' cues and emotional needs, as well as from lower sensitivity in early interactions (Murray et al., 2014). Breastfeeding may also be negatively affected, as these mothers are more likely to decide not to breastfeed or to report lower perceived self-efficacy when doing so (Fallon et al., 2016).

Suicidal ideation in the perinatal period

Suicidal ideation is a particularly prominent issue during both the antenatal and postpartum periods, ranging from thoughts of ending

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one's life to planning suicide (WHO, 2019; 2022).

Despite the popular belief that pregnancy is a protective factor against suicide, it may actually be more prevalent among pregnant women than in the general female population (Gavin et al., 2011; Gelaye et al., 2016). Depressive symptomatology and anxiety are the psychological conditions most frequently associated with suicidal ideation (Bodnar-Deren et al., 2016).

The diathesis-stress model has been the most commonly used framework to explain antenatal suicidal ideation, highlighting two key dimensions: biological vulnerabilities (e.g., genetic predispositions, biochemical disorders, brain abnormalities) and interrelated psychosocial factors, including psychological disorders, a history of abuse, socioeconomic stressors, and social isolation, which together may facilitate the onset of suicidal ideation and behaviour (Gelaye et al., 2016).

Similarly, Reid et al. (2022) propose a complementary model focused on pregnancy and postpartum suggesting that mothers' perceived difficulties in coping with motherhood, feeling 'attacked by motherhood', isolated, or trapped, can lead them to view themselves as 'bad mothers' and consider suicide as the only option.

Identified risk factors for suicidal ideation during the perinatal stage include: prior or current mental health issues (especially depression), poor sleep, intimate relationship violence, trauma exposure, low socioeconomic status, stressful life events, substance use, and abortion history, applicable to both the antenatal and postpartum periods (Bright et al., 2022; O'Connor et al., 2018).

Despite this information, suicidal ideation continues to be a taboo subject that is difficult to study (Castelao et al., 2022). Furthermore, little is known about protective factors. There are factors that have been shown to be protective against suicide in the general population, including social relationships, well-being or having young children to care for (WHO, 2014).

Regarding perinatal stage, well-being variables have been identified as essential protective factors. Many theories distinguish between hedonic and psychological well-being. Hedonic well-being includes both affective components (i.e., positive emotions) and cognitive components (life satisfaction or overall evaluations of one's life) (Diener et al., 1985). On the other hand, psychological well-being addresses the psychological resources involved in the search for meaning to life, positive relationships, personal growth and realization of the maximum potential of the individual (Ryff, 1989). Both components of well-being (i.e., hedonic and eudaimonic), although related, can be differentiated from one another (Joshani, 2019).

In this context, Wouk et al. (2019) observed that experiencing positive emotions while feeding their children reduces the risk of developing depressive or anxious symptoms and, in cases where such symptoms do occur, their intensity is reduced. In relation to psychological well-being, research indicates that higher levels of maternal psychological well-being are associated with lower levels of postpartum depression, anxiety, and stress (Matvienko-Sikar & Dockray, 2017). Additionally, prenatal social support correlates with reduced anxiety and depression, a greater sense of control over pregnancy-related changes, improved self-image, and better health (Hajure et al., 2024).

Although most evidence comes from international samples, understanding suicidal ideation among Spanish women is crucial due to cultural and healthcare specificities. In Spain, 14-23 % of women experience depressive symptoms during pregnancy, rising to 22-30 % postpartum (Rodríguez-Muñoz et al., 2023). It is also worth noting that perinatal mental health problems in Spain are often underdiagnosed, as universal screening protocols are lacking and access to psychological care remains limited (Rodríguez-Muñoz et al., 2023).

Thus, this study aims to explore the characteristics of suicidal ideation in Spanish women suffering from postpartum depression, as well as to examine risk and protective factors. To achieve this, the following specific objectives were proposed: 1) to determine the prevalence of suicidal ideation among women with postpartum depression; 2) to

explore risk and protective variables at the sociodemographic level (i.e., age, education level), perinatal level (i.e., maternal health during pregnancy, baby temperament) and psychological level (i.e., anxiety-depressive symptomatology, psychological well-being); 3) to propose an explanatory model of suicidal ideation in the perinatal stage and, 4) to identify possible moderating factors in the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation.

Based on the literature reviewed, it is expected that: 1) the prevalence of puerperal suicidal ideation will be approximately 20 % (Martínez et al., 2024); 2) risk factors will be identified, including education level, history of psychological issues and exposure to stressful events (Bright et al., 2022; O'Connor et al., 2018), as well as protective factors such as life satisfaction, psychological well-being and social support (WHO, 2014); 3) suicidal ideation will be explained by socio-demographic, perinatal, and psychological factors (Gelaye et al., 2016; Reid et al., 2022); 4) social support, stressful life events, and certain pregnancy and postpartum-related variables will moderate the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation (Akram et al., 2020; Bright et al., 2022).

Methods

Ethical considerations

All procedures carried out in this project, as well as the collection of personal data, complied with the ethical standards of the institutional research committee (Ref.: CE_20211216-05_SOC) and the 2024 amendment to the Declaration of Helsinki. The committee evaluated the suitability of the study protocol in relation to its objectives, the justification of any foreseeable risks or discomfort for participants, and the adequacy of the procedures for obtaining informed consent. It also assessed the qualifications of the research team and the measures in place to ensure data confidentiality in accordance with current data protection regulations. During the approval process, particular attention was paid to the sensitive nature of the personal and emotional data collected, ensuring that risks were minimized and that procedures for managing potential distress were clearly defined. Given the involvement of a vulnerable sample, all personal and clinical information was stored anonymously and used exclusively for research purposes, and kept in secure, access-restricted locations in full compliance with EU GDPR requirements and national data protection laws.

Participants

The sample consisted of 91 Spanish women aged 18 years or older who scored 11 or higher on the Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale (Cox et al., 1987) and had given birth within the past year. The EPDS cut-off of ≥ 11 was selected based on evidence supporting its optimal sensitivity and specificity for identifying major depression in perinatal populations (Levis et al., 2020).

Participants were excluded if they: a) had given birth in the past month (potential 'baby blues'); b) met DSM-5 criteria for substance abuse and/or dependence within the 30 days prior to study participation, or c) had a serious mental disorder (e.g., severe neurocognitive problems or brain damage, psychotic disorders). Regarding age, the mean was 34.03 years (SD = 4.30). The sociodemographic characteristics of the participants are shown in Table 1.

Instruments

Sociodemographic questionnaire and perinatal stage information. Participants provided information about their age, stable partner status, level of education, employment status prior to childbirth, number of children, and postpartum months. Stable partner status refers only to current cohabitation with a partner or legal marital situation. They were also asked about aspects related to pregnancy (e.g., complications

Table 1
Sociodemographic characteristics of the sample.

	N = 91
Age	34.03 (SD = 4.30)
Stable partner status:	
Married or living with partner	89 (97.8 %)
Separated or divorced	1 (1.1 %)
Single	1 (1.1 %)
Level of education:	
University studies	74 (81.3 %)
Vocational training	16 (17.6 %)
Secondary education	1 (1.1 %)
Employment status before childbirth:	
Employed	59 (64.8 %)
Homemaker	4 (4.4 %)
Unemployed	10 (11 %)
Student	2 (2.2 %)
On sick leave	16 (17.6 %)
Number of children:	
One	69 (75.8 %)
Two	19 (20.9 %)
Three	3 (3.3 %)
More than three	0 (0 %)
Postpartum trimester:	
First trimester	32 (35.2 %)
Second trimester	34 (37.4 %)
Third trimester	15 (16.5 %)
Fourth trimester	10 (10.9 %)

during pregnancy, anxiety and depression during pregnancy), childbirth (e.g., type of birth) and postpartum period (e.g., mother's sleep, child's temperament). These sociodemographic and perinatal questions were based on the Postpartum Depression Predictors Inventory-Revised (PDPI-R; Beck et al., 2002).

The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS; Cox et al., 1987) is a ten-item self-administered tool used for screening postpartum depression. The response format is a Likert-type scale with 4 response levels, ranging from 1 ('never') to 4 ('very often') (García-Esteve et al., 2003). This scale is frequently used to assess suicidal ideation by analyzing responses to item 10 (i.e., *The thought of harming myself has occurred to me*) (García-Esteve et al., 2003). For the analysis of prevalence, suicidal ideation was considered present when participants answered, 'hardly ever', 'sometimes' or 'very often', whereas only the answer 'never' was categorized as absence of suicidal ideation. For all other analyses, the item was analysed as a continuous variable. The EPDS comprises three subscales: anhedonia, anxiety and depression (López-Janer et al., 2021). Regarding its reliability, Cronbach's alpha was $\alpha = .73$.

The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS; Watson et al., 1988) is used to measure both positive and negative affect through twenty items (ten for each factor). The response format is a five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 ('not at all or very slightly') to 5 ('a lot') (López-Gómez et al., 2015). Regarding its reliability, the positive affect factor had a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = .86$ and the negative affect factor had a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = .81$.

The Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS; Diener et al., 1985) is used to assess general life satisfaction through five items. The response format is a Likert-type scale with seven response options, ranging from 1 ('strongly disagree') to 7 ('strongly agree') (Vázquez et al., 2013). Regarding its reliability, Cronbach's alpha was $\alpha = .88$.

The Psychological Well-Being Scale (PWB; Ryff, 1989) assesses well-being based on the dimensions proposed by Ryff, which are: autonomy ($\alpha = .86$), personal growth ($\alpha = .80$), positive relationships ($\alpha = .81$), competence ($\alpha = .62$), self-acceptance ($\alpha = .80$) and purpose in life ($\alpha = .73$). There are two versions (Díaz et al., 2006), of which the twenty-nine-item version was used in the present study. The response format used is a six-point Likert scale from 1 ('strongly disagree') to 6 ('strongly agree') (Díaz et al., 2006).

The Postpartum Bonding Questionnaire (PBQ; Brockington et al.,

2001) is a twenty-five-item tool used to assess the mother-child bond. It is suitable for detecting deterioration of this bond (García-Esteve et al., 2016). The response format is a six-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 ('never') to 6 ('always') (García-Esteve et al., 2016). It has four subscales (García-Esteve et al., 2016), which are: bonding problems ($\alpha = .73$), rejection and risk of abuse towards the baby ($\alpha = .73$), lack of enjoyment and affection for the baby ($\alpha = .82$) and anxiety about care ($\alpha = .83$).

The Maternal Efficacy Questionnaire (MEQ; Teti & Gelfand, 1991) evaluates, through ten items, women's perceived efficacy in a series of scenarios related to the care of their child. The response format is a Likert-like scale with four alternatives, ranging from 1 ('not good') to 4 ('very good') (Teti & Gelfand, 1991). Regarding its reliability, its Cronbach's alpha was $\alpha = .82$.

The Pregnancy Related Beliefs Questionnaire (PRBQ; Leach et al., 2018) is an eight-item scale designed to assess mothers' maladaptive attitudes about their performance in relation to their child. It has proven useful in identifying women at risk of developing postpartum depression (Leach et al., 2017). The response format is a seven-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 ('strongly agree') to 7 ('strongly disagree') (Leach et al., 2017). Regarding its reliability, its Cronbach's alpha was $\alpha = .73$.

Stressful life events and social support were assessed using questions from the Postpartum Depression Predictors Inventory (PDPI-R; Beck, 2002). These questions are answered using a dichotomous scale (i.e., 'yes' or 'no'). Life events were evaluated with seven questions related to economic and marital problems, the death of a family member, unemployment, the occurrence of a serious illness in a family member, residential changes, or switching jobs. Social support was assessed using seven questions related to emotional or practical support from the partner or family members (e.g., *Do you think you receive adequate emotional support from your family?*).

Procedure

Participants were recruited in Spain through social media posts and referrals from primary care midwives working in the public healthcare system. Recruitment took place between 2021 and 2024 and followed a non-probabilistic convenience sampling strategy combining community and clinical sources. Primary care midwives conducted an initial screening using the EPDS scale to identify women showing depressive symptoms suitable for referral to the research team.

After referral by midwives or voluntary contact through social media, all potential participants received an email from the research team containing a detailed explanation of the study's objectives and an informed consent form. Once consent was provided, they completed an online EPDS screening via the Qualtrics platform to confirm the presence of symptoms. Subsequently, a telephone interview was conducted by a team of licensed clinical psychologists trained in perinatal mental health to verify inclusion and exclusion criteria, assess symptom severity, and ensure participant safety throughout the process. A suicide risk assessment and a prevention plan were implemented for women identified as being at high risk, and they were informed about the relevant emergency services. Eligible participants then completed the study's full evaluation protocol, which included additional online questionnaires administered through Qualtrics. Finally, all study participants were given the option to receive free psychological intervention in a group format.

Data analysis

First, descriptive analyses were conducted to calculate the mean and standard deviation for the quantitative variables and the frequency (both absolute and relative) for the qualitative variables. Pearson's bivariate correlations were also computed between the scores on item 10 of the EPDS (suicidal ideation) and continuous variables (e.g., age) to assess the presence of any significant relationship between them.

Additionally, a series of Student's t-tests for independent samples were performed to compare the scores on item 10 of the EPDS between groups defined by dichotomous variables (e.g., chronic illness). An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was also performed to evaluate whether there were differences between groups formed by categorical variables (e.g., employment status) in the mean scores of item 10 of the EPDS. Bonferroni correction was used to control for Type I error across multiple comparisons.

To develop an explanatory model, a multiple linear regression analysis was performed after verifying the assumptions of regression, which include: (a) linearity, (b) independence, (c) normality, and (d) non-collinearity. The dependent variable was the score on item 10 of the EPDS, which corresponds to suicidal ideation. The independent variables included all those that had shown a significant relationship with the dependent variable.

To assess whether social support, stressful life events or pregnancy and postpartum-related variables moderated the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation, a series of moderation analyses were conducted. The variables investigated as potential moderating factors included: (a) depression during pregnancy, (b) anxiety during pregnancy, (c) planned pregnancy, (d) miscarriages, (e) baby's health during pregnancy, (f) baby's sleep, (g) mother's health during pregnancy, (h) mother's sleep during the postpartum period, (i) infant feeding problems, (j) infant temperament, (k) infant crying, (l) difficulties in comforting the infant, (m) social support, and (n) stressful life events (all dichotomous variables).

The dataset was complete with no missing observations in the analyzed variables. Therefore, no imputation procedures were required.

All statistical analyses were performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 25.0 (SPSS). Moderation analyses were conducted using Process Macro for SPSS (Hayes, 2022).

Results

First, the prevalence of suicidal ideation in women with postpartum depression was 27.5 %. Considering the postpartum trimester, it was observed that suicidal ideation was present in 28.12 % of mothers who were in the first postpartum trimester, 20.59 % in the second trimester, 46.67 % in the third trimester and 20 % in the fourth trimester. However, no statistically significant differences were found in suicidal ideation across postpartum trimesters (i.e., first, second, third, and fourth trimester) [$F(3,87) = 2.009, p > .05, \eta^2 = .07$]. Furthermore, no statistically significant differences were found [$F(2,88) = 1.316, p > .05$] when examining levels of suicidal ideation across different years of assessment (i.e., 2022, 2023, and 2024).

Analysis of the correlations between suicidal ideation and sociodemographic, perinatal and psychological variables

To assess the relationship between suicidal ideation and continuous variables, a series of bivariate Pearson correlation analyses were conducted. The results are presented in Table 2. Significant positive correlations were found between suicidal ideation and the following variables: (a) number of children, (b) total bonding score with the baby (PBQ), (c) the subscales of rejection and risk of abuse, care anxiety, and bonding problems (PBQ), and (d) the anxiety and depression subscales of the EPDS. Conversely, significant negative correlations were found between suicidal ideation and the following variables: (a) the competence subscale of the PWB and, (b) the total score on the SWLS.

Differences in suicidal ideation according to dichotomous and categorical variables are presented in Table 3.

A higher score on suicidal ideation was observed among mothers who experienced depression during pregnancy compared to those who did not [$t(65.90) = -2.106, p < .05, d = -.45$]. Similarly, mothers who described their baby's temperament as irritable had a higher score on suicidal ideation than those women who did not perceive their child this

way [$t(27.46) = -2.308, p < .05, d = -.57$]. A higher score on suicidal ideation was also found among mothers who reported postpartum sleep problems compared to those who did not experience such problems [$t(88.64) = -2.768, p < .05, d = -.60$]. Additionally, although significant differences were observed in suicidal ideation scores for the prepartum employment status variable, post hoc testing revealed no significant differences between any pair of categories. Finally, for the remaining variables studied, no statistically significant differences were found in the suicidal ideation score.

Multiple linear regression analysis

In the multiple linear regression analysis, suicidal ideation (item 10 of the EPDS) served as the dependent variable. Independent variables included those that showed a significant correlation with suicidal ideation.

To do this, compliance with the regression assumptions was first verified. First, normality was assumed based on the sample size ($N > 50$). Linearity, which requires a linear relationship between the variables, was also assumed based on the distribution of scores in the scatter plot. The Durbin-Watson statistic was used to verify compliance with the independence assumption. Considering its value ($D = 1.87$), which falls within the acceptable range of 1.5 to 2.5, the residuals of the predictor variables were assumed to be independent. Regarding non-collinearity, variance inflation factors (VIF) were below 5 and tolerance values were above .10. Therefore, this assumption was also considered to be met, indicating no multicollinearity issues.

The results of the regression analysis are presented in Table 4. The linear regression model explained 29.3 % of the total variance in suicidal ideation ($R^2 = .29$), and the final model was statistically significant [$F(3) = 12.002, p < .001$].

The variables that explained suicidal ideation were: number of children ($t = 3.107, p = .003$), the EPDS depression subscale ($t = 2.362, p = .02$) and the PBQ bonding problems subscale ($t = 3.127, p = .002$).

On the other hand, mother's sleep problems, depression during pregnancy, baby's irritable temperament, postpartum anxiety, anxiety about care, rejection and risk of abuse toward the baby, competence and life satisfaction did not obtain statistically significant results.

Analysis of moderating variables in the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation

Regarding the search for moderating variables, among all the dichotomous variables assessed (i.e., social support, stressful life events, variables related to pregnancy and postpartum), the following were identified as moderators: (a) emotional support from family, (b) presence of economic problems, (c) anxiety during pregnancy and (d) baby's irritable temperament. In other words, the presence or absence of these variables changed the strength of the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation.

Table 5 presents the results of the significant moderation analyses. The effect of anxiety during pregnancy on the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation is illustrated in Fig. 1. The moderating effects of family emotional support, economic problems and baby's temperament are shown in Figs. 2-4, respectively.

Discussion

The main aim of this study was to examine suicidal ideation in women with postpartum depression, including its risk and protective factors. Such research is crucial given the prevalence of suicidal ideation during the perinatal period and its potential impact on mothers, infants, and their broader environment (Bright et al., 2022; Gelaye et al., 2016; WHO, 2022).

Regarding the first specific objective, it was found that 27.5 % of participants reported suicidal ideation, with the highest prevalence

Table 2
Results of bivariate correlation analyses.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
1	-																								
2	.06	-																							
3	.30**	.30**	-																						
4	.02	-.02	-.10	-																					
5	.01	-.10	-.06	.06	-																				
6	.12	-.10	-.07	.11	.05	-																			
7	-.07	.02	-.04	.06	.09	-.53**	-																		
8	.34**	-.09	-.05	.10	-.04	.50**	-.61**	-																	
9	.36**	-.07	-.10	-.03	.03	.49**	-.61**	.89**	-																
10	.29**	-.13	-.02	.12	-.03	.49**	-.54**	.91**	.71**	-															
11	.13	.10	.05	-.01	-.15	.16	-.43**	.64**	.52**	.39**	-														
12	.26*	-.16	-.08	.30**	-.02	.35**	-.25*	.70**	.46**	.61**	.33**	-													
13	-.26*	.01	-.04	-.04	.43**	-.18	.22*	-.45**	-.37**	-.45**	-.29**	-.28**	-												
14	-.11	-.02	-.16	-.08	.30**	-.07	.23*	-.18	-.09	-.22*	-.17	-.03	.30**	-											
15	.20	.01	.24*	.13	-.24*	.34**	-.24*	.31**	.26*	.34*	.05	.28**	-.35**	-.24*	-										
16	-.20	-.20	-.21	-.15	.29**	-.40**	.45**	-.41**	-.37**	-.34**	-.42**	-.18	.57**	.30**	-.40**	-									
17	-.11	-.09	-.14	-.01	.23*	-.39**	.37**	-.42**	-.40**	-.37**	-.30**	-.26*	.62**	.30**	-.44**	.85**	-								
18	-.14	-.15	-.27*	-.15	.34**	-.14	.28**	-.13	-.07	-.10	-.27*	-.02	.22*	.34**	-.36**	.67**	.47**	-							
19	-.19	-.20	-.06	-.21	-.03	-.36**	.27*	-.25*	-.25*	-.18	-.30**	-.06	.15	.03	-.14	.67**	.43**	.32**	-						
20	-.28**	-.03	-.16	-.07	.34**	-.32**	.34**	-.53**	-.52**	-.48**	-.31**	-.33**	.77**	.25*	-.44**	.71**	.66**	.36**	.23*	-					
21	-.07	-.21*	-.15	.01	.34**	-.27**	.42**	-.30**	-.29**	-.25*	-.31**	-.07	.62**	.26*	-.27**	.81**	.74**	.39**	.33**	.67**	-				
22	-.03	-.14	-.17	-.18	.15	-.25*	.34**	-.26*	-.17	-.20	-.35**	-.16	.34**	.24*	-.20	.69**	.57**	.34**	.29**	.46**	.62**	-			
23	.02	.17	.08	-.07	-.22*	.22*	-.21	.20	.20	.17	-.16	.07	-.29**	-.38**	.15	-.24*	-.31**	-.18	.07	-.25*	-.27**	-.29*	-		
24	.32**	.10	.14	.26*	-.18	.16	-.02	.18	.13	.21*	.04	.16	-.36**	-.17	.41**	-.30**	-.31**	-.16	-.15	-.36**	-.23*	-.18	.12	-	
25	.40**	.02	.18	-.06	-.40**	.33**	-.31**	.41**	.44**	.44**	.17	.23*	-.61**	-.32**	.47**	-.45**	-.41**	-.26	-.20	-.56**	-.42**	-.23	.36**	.37**	

Note. 1 = suicidal ideation, 2 = age, 3 = number of children, 4 = postpartum months, 5 = total score on social support, 6 = beliefs related to motherhood (total score PBRQ); 7 = maternal self-efficacy (total score on MEQ); 8 = postpartum bonding (total score PBQ); 9 = bonding problems subscale (PBQ); 10 = care anxiety subscale (PBQ); 11 = lack of enjoyment and affection for the baby subscale (PBQ); 12 = rejection and abuse risk subscale (PBQ); 13 = satisfaction with life (total score SWLS); 14 = positive PANAS subscale; 15 = negative PANAS subscale; 16 = psychological well-being (total score PWB); 17 = self-acceptance subscale (PWB); 18 = positive relationships subscale (PWB); 19 = autonomy subscale (PWB); 20 = competence subscale (PWB); 21 = purpose subscale (PWB); 22 = growth subscale (PWB); 23 = anhedonia subscale (EPDS), 24 = anxiety subscale (EPDS), 25 = depression subscale (EPDS).

* $p < .05$ (bilateral)
** $p < .001$ (bilateral).

Table 3
Results of Student's t-tests and one-factor ANOVA for analyzing differences in suicidal ideation.

	N	M	SD	t/F	p	d/ η ²
Stable partner status:		X	2X			
Single	1	1	-	1.85	.16	.04
Married / living with partner	89	.46	.84			
Divorced / Separated	1	2	-			
Level of education:		X	X			
Secondary education	1	.00	-	.41	.67	.01
Vocational training	16	.63	.96			
University studies	74	.46	.83			
Employment status before childbirth:		X	X			
Employed	59	.53	.86	2.74	.03	.11
Homemaker	4	1.25	.96			
Unemployed	10	.00	.00			
Student	2	1.50	2.12			
On sick leave	16	.31	.70			
Postpartum trimester:						
First trimester	32	.47	.84	2.01	.12	.07
Second trimester	34	.38	.78			
Third trimester	15	.93	1.10			
Fourth trimester	10	.20	.42			
Chronic disease:		X	X			
No	69	.46	.82	-.39	.70	-.09
Yes	22	.55	.96			
Complications in childbirth:		X	X			
No	65	.49	.83	.15	.88	.03
Yes	26	.46	.91			
Mother's health during pregnancy:		X	X			
Poor	4	.50	1.00	.11	.95	.00
Regular	15	.40	.74			
Good	37	.54	.90			
Very good	35	.46	.85			
Baby's health during pregnancy:		X	X			
Poor	0	-	-	2.97	.06	.06
Regular	2	.00	.00			
Good	21	.86	1.06			
Very good	68	.38	.75			
Depression during pregnancy:		X	X			
No	51	.31	.68	-2.11	.04	-.45
Yes	40	.70	.99			
Anxiety during pregnancy:		X	X			
No	23	.35	.71	-.89	.38	-.21
Yes	68	.53	.89			
Planned pregnancy:		X	X			
No	25	.76	1.01	1.71	.10	.40
Yes	66	.38	.76			
Previous abortions:		X	X			
No	74	.46	.83	-.56	.58	-.15
Yes	17	.59	.94			
Type of birth:		X	X			
Natural	47	.36	.76	.89	.45	.03
Natural with instrumentation	20	.60	.99			
Unscheduled cesarean section	21	.57	.87			
Scheduled cesarean section	3	1.00	1.00			
Baby's sleep problems:		X	X			
No	48	.38	.79	-1.30	.20	-.27
Yes	43	.60	.90			
Mother's sleep problems:		X	X			
No	34	.21	.59	-2.77	.01	-.60
Yes	57	.65	.94			
Baby's feeding problems:		X	X			
No	72	.49	.86	.06	.96	.02
Yes	19	.47	.84			
Baby's irritable temperament:		X	X			
No	69	.35	.72	-2.31	.03	-.57
Yes	22	.91	1.07			
Frequent infant crying:		X	X			
No	71	.45	.86	-.69	.49	-.17
Yes	20	.60	.82			
Problems comforting the baby:		X	X			
No	74	.39	.77	-1.81	.09	-.49
Yes	17	.88	1.05			
Emotional support from partner:		X	X			

Table 3 (continued)

	N	M	SD	t/F	p	d/ η ²
No	49	.55	.89	.82	.42	.17
Yes	42	.40	.80			
Practical support from partner:		X	X			
No	34	.35	.81	-1.16	.25	-.25
Yes	57	.56	.87			
Emotional support from family:		X	X			
No	52	.62	.93	1.81	.07	.38
Yes	39	.31	.69			
Practical support from family:		X	X			
No	44	.43	.82	-.56	.58	-.12
Yes	47	.53	.88			
Emotional support from friends:		X	X			
No	36	.61	.90	1.16	.25	.25
Yes	55	.40	.81			
Practical support from friends:		X	X			
No	61	.39	.76	-1.33	.19	-.30
Yes	30	.67	.99			
Satisfaction with partner:		X	X			
No	35	.37	.77	-.99	.32	-.21
Yes	56	.55	.89			
Economic problems:		X	X			
No	73	.42	.76	-1.06	.30	-.28
Yes	18	.72	1.13			
Family member's death in the past year:		X	X			
No	73	.44	.83	-1.02	.31	-.27
Yes	18	.67	.91			
Moving in the past year:		X	X			
No	65	.55	.90	1.42	.16	.33
Yes	26	.31	.68			
Job change in the past year:		X	X			
No	71	.55	.89	1.68	.10	.43
Yes	20	.25	.64			

Table 4
Results of multiple linear regression analysis.

Model	Beta	Standard error	t	p	f ²
Number of children	.47	.15	3.11	.00	.11
Mother's sleep problems	.16	.17	1.62	.11	.02
Depression during pregnancy	.07	.17	.77	.45	.01
Baby's irritable temperament	.12	.21	1.21	.23	.02
Depression (EPDS)	.27	.12	2.36	.02	.06
Anxiety (EPDS)	.18	.22	1.82	.07	.04
Anxiety about care (PBQ)	-.05	.04	-.40	.69	.00
Bonding problems (PBQ)	.05	.02	3.13	.00	.11
Rejection and risk of abuse (PBQ)	.11	.05	1.11	.27	.01
Competence (PWB)	.11	.04	.88	.38	.01
Satisfaction with life (SWLS)	.01	.02	.16	.87	.00

observed in the first and third postpartum trimesters. This result partially confirms the hypothesis, as it aligns closely with the initial expectations. Suicidal ideation among women with postpartum depression appears to be higher than in the general population (Martínez et al., 2024). This finding is consistent with previous studies, such as the one conducted by Chen et al. (2023), where the prevalence of suicidal ideation was higher in women with postpartum depression compared to those without it. Furthermore, the increase in prevalence could also be attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic, an event that significantly contributed to the rise in suicidal ideation among women (Urdiales & Sánchez, 2021).

In relation to the second specific objective, various risk and protective factors were identified. Regarding sociodemographic variables, number of children was found to be a risk factor for suicidal ideation in this study. This finding is inconsistent with previous literature, where it has been identified as a protective factor against suicide (WHO, 2014). However, it is possible that this variable contributes to the onset of suicidal ideation in women with postpartum depression, as having a larger number of children may increase the psychological burden

Table 5

Regression analysis to evaluate the moderators of the relationship between postpartum depressive symptoms and suicidal ideation.

	β	SE(B)	t	p	R ²	ΔR^2	F	p	f ²
Moderator: Emotional family support									
DV: suicidal ideation.									
Step 1.									
Depressive symptoms (X)	.41	.11	3.73	<.001	.24	.24	9.01	<.001	.32
Emotional family support (Z)	.90	.43	2.10	.04					
Step 2.									
X*Z (interaction)	-.61	.22	-2.74	.01	.31	.07	7.54	.007	.45
Moderator: Economic problems									
DV: suicidal ideation.									
Step 1.									
Depressive symptoms (X)	.65	.14	4.57	<.001	.21	.21	7.79	<.001	.27
Economic problems (Z)	-1.21	.61	-1.97	.05					
Step 2.									
X*Z (interaction)	.66	.28	2.32	.02	.26	.05	5.40	.02	.35
Moderator: Anxiety during pregnancy									
DV: suicidal ideation.									
Step 1.									
Depressive symptoms (X)	.27	.13	2.11	.04	.23	.23	8.65	<.001	.30
Anxious symptoms (Z)	-1.11	.49	-2.27	.03					
Step 2.									
X*Z (interaction)	.71	.26	2.74	.01	.30	.07	7.49	.008	.43
Moderator: Irritable temperament									
DV: suicidal ideation.									
Step 1.									
Depressive symptoms (X)	.60	.14	4.38	<.001	.25	.25	9.53	<.001	.33
Irritable temperament (Z)	-1.15	.61	-1.90	.06					
Step 2.									
X*Z (interaction)	.72	.28	2.61	.01	.31	.06	6.83	.011	.45

Fig. 1. Anxiety during pregnancy as a moderator of the relationship between suicidal ideation (EPDS item 10) and postpartum depression (EPDS depression subscale).

experienced in this condition. In addition, a higher number of children may exacerbate socioeconomic stressors and lead to social isolation, given the amount of care they require. These variables have traditionally been associated with higher levels of suicidal ideation (Gelaye et al., 2016).

Regarding psychological variables, depressive symptomatology during pregnancy, anxiety-depressive symptomatology postpartum and mother's sleep problems have been identified as risk factors. These results are consistent with both the hypothesis and previous literature (Bright et al., 2022; Gelaye et al., 2016; O'Connor et al., 2018).

Furthermore, this study has identified a series of risk factors not previously addressed in the existing literature, such as bonding

problems with the baby, anxiety about care, rejection and risk of abuse towards the baby, and baby's irritable temperament. However, these results align with the explanatory theory of perinatal suicide proposed by Reid et al. (2022). In this sense, difficulties in bonding with the baby, anxiety with caregiving, and feelings of rejection towards the infant could contribute to the phenomenon described by Reid et al. (2022) as feeling 'attacked by motherhood', which may facilitate the onset of suicidal ideation.

Regarding protective factors, satisfaction with life and a sense of competence were found to protect mothers from suicidal ideation. Both variables have been shown to play a significant role in safeguarding against depressive symptomatology during the perinatal stage (WHO,

Fig. 2. Emotional family support as a moderator of the relationship between suicidal ideation (EPDS item 10) and postpartum depression (EPDS depression subscale).

Fig. 3. Economic problems as a moderator of the relationship between suicidal ideation (EPDS item 10) and postpartum depression (EPDS depression subscale).

2014). Therefore, feeling competent in tasks related to caring for their child may serve as a protective factor against suicidal ideation during this period (Reid et al., 2022).

In relation to the third specific objective, it was found that suicidal ideation could be explained by postpartum depression, bonding problems with the baby and number of children, which partially aligns with the established hypothesis. In this context, both depressive symptomatology and difficulty in bonding with their child are aspects reflected in the proposals of Gelaye et al. (2016) and Reid et al. (2022). However, other variables, such as mother's sleep problems, baby's irritable temperament, life satisfaction and sense of competence lose their explanatory role when they are simultaneously introduced into the model. This lack of significance may be due to the limited variability in the sample, the stronger influence of depressive and anxiety symptoms, or potential indirect pathways not captured in the current model. Some nonsignificant variables may also have been affected by the measurement methods, such as the use of self-report instruments with limited sensitivity. Additionally, certain factors—such as infant irritable

temperament—may not exert a direct effect but could still moderate the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation, highlighting their potential relevance within the broader psychosocial context. Nevertheless, these factors may still contribute to postpartum risk and warrant further investigation in larger samples or longitudinal studies.

In relation to the fourth specific objective, the analysis revealed that lack of emotional support from family, experiencing economic difficulties, suffering from anxiety during pregnancy and baby's irritable temperament moderated the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation. In other words, postpartum depression is associated with suicidal ideation, but when the woman perceives a lack of emotional support of her family, experiences economic problems, suffers from anxiety during pregnancy and/or has a baby with an irritable temperament, this relationship becomes stronger and the impact of postpartum depression on suicidal ideation is greater. A possible explanation for these moderating effects is that both antenatal anxiety and infant irritability may intensify maternal stress and perceived

Fig. 4. Baby's temperament as a moderator of the relationship between suicidal ideation (EPDS item 10) and postpartum depression (EPDS depression subscale).

caregiving burden, thereby amplifying the emotional impact of depressive symptoms on suicidal ideation. Difficult infant temperament can heighten feelings of inadequacy and exhaustion, particularly among mothers already experiencing anxiety or limited support, which may increase vulnerability to suicidal thoughts.

In this regard, the results related to family support and stressful life events are consistent with prior research by authors such as Akram et al. (2020) or Bright et al. (2022). However, the moderating roles of the baby's irritable temperament and anxiety during pregnancy had not previously been considered as potentially influencing the relationship between postpartum depression and suicidal ideation. Therefore, further replication of these results is necessary to verify their moderating effects.

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. Firstly, it is a cross-sectional study, which means that causal relationships cannot be established between the variables studied. Nevertheless, it is possible to hypothesize how these associations might unfold over time. For instance, it could be expected that a higher number of children would lead to increased depressive symptoms over time, which in turn, could impair the mother–infant bond and, ultimately contributing to the emergence of suicidal ideation (Shi et al., 2018). Secondly, the majority of the sample were university students and were either married or lived with their partner, which limits the generalizability of the findings to women who do not share these sociodemographic characteristics. This profile may reflect a population with greater access to resources, higher health literacy, and stronger social support networks than the general population, potentially reducing the variability in psychological risk factors observed. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted with caution when extrapolating to women with lower educational attainment or without partner support. It should also be noted that women within the first month after childbirth were not included, which may limit the understanding of psychological adjustment during the earliest postpartum phase. Thirdly, although the model identified significant predictors of puerperal suicidal ideation, the proportion of explained variance was only moderate, indicating that other unmeasured biological (e.g., postpartum complications), psychosocial (e.g., maternal coping skills, childhood experiences, religious beliefs), perinatal (e.g., breastfeeding status), or contextual factors (e.g., access to mental health care, socioeconomic inequalities) may also contribute to this phenomenon and should be addressed in future research. Regarding the instruments employed, the reliability of some of the scales was not sufficiently high, which may limit the accuracy of the results. Some

moderators (e.g., economic problems, social support) were assessed using dichotomous items from the Postpartum Depression Predictors Inventory, which may have limited variability and reduced sensitivity in these measures. Finally, results related to the homoscedasticity assumption of the linear regression model suggest the potential presence of heteroscedasticity, indicating possible errors in the regression estimates.

Despite these limitations, this study is expected to serve as a foundation for future research on the characterization of suicidal ideation in women with postpartum depression. In this regard, the present work contributes to a deeper understanding of the risk factors associated with suicidal ideation. It also sheds light on protective factors by incorporating well-being variables into the measurement protocols. These findings enable a more efficient identification of women who are vulnerable due to multiple risk factors. This, in turn, lays the groundwork for the development of evaluation protocols focused on these factors and the creation of early action plans to reduce, as much as possible, the onset of puerperal suicidal ideation and its consequences for both the mother's and the baby's health. Additionally, identifying protective factors allows for their inclusion in psychological interventions. In this regard, this study provides new insights to advance research on prevention and intervention strategies for mothers in this situation. Programs targeting modifiable psychological and contextual factors identified in our study may help mitigate suicidal ideation in postpartum women. Specifically, interventions focused on reducing depressive symptoms and enhancing mother–infant bonding could directly address the key predictors identified. Programs that promote maternal sense of competence and provide structured emotional and social support may further buffer the risk associated with these factors. Interventions integrating positive psychology techniques or parenting competence training have shown promising results in improving maternal well-being and reducing depressive symptoms (Haga et al., 2021; Matvienko-Sikar & Dockray, 2017). Mindfulness-based interventions have also proven effective in enhancing emotional regulation and preventing psychological distress during the perinatal period (Guo et al., 2020). Tailoring such interventions to the specific needs highlighted by our findings could maximize their preventive impact on postpartum suicidal ideation.

Future research should consider conducting longitudinal studies to examine the relationship between the studied variables over an extended period, thus establishing causal links between them and suicidal ideation. This will help refine interventions and identify key

therapeutic targets. In addition, investigating variables not included in the present study (for example, aspects of the mother's childhood) could provide valuable insights into their potential impact on perinatal suicidal ideation and enhance our understanding of this still under-researched phenomenon.

In conclusion, this study represents a starting point for more comprehensive research into the characteristics, as well as the risk and protective factors, of women who suffer from postpartum depression and experience suicidal ideation. It is hoped that it will contribute to the development of early assessment and intervention protocols that address these factors, with the goal of preventing the onset of suicidal ideation and its consequences for both mothers and their babies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alma Pérez: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Elisa Nombela:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Almudena Duque:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Covadonga Chaves:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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